

This document contains the qualification survey for the “Understanding the Functions of the Review Process in the Era of Agentic Development” paper. Options **highlighted in yellow** indicate the selection criteria for participants and result in rejection. If a participant met all the criteria, they were provided with a link to schedule an interview.

Introduction

Hi,

We’re researching how AI is reshaping code review. For this study, we’re looking for developers interested in sharing their experience.

If you’d like to participate, please fill out the form below. We’ll contact you to arrange a **one-hour video interview** if your background matches our research criteria.

The anonymized results of this study will help us gain new insights into how programming practices are evolving and inform future education efforts.

As a token of our appreciation for taking part in the interview, you will receive your choice of either a USD 100 Amazon Gift Card or a one-year subscription to **Company Name¹** products, or you will have the option to donate USD 100 to a charity of your choice.

Completing the form should take no more than five minutes. All information you provide will be kept confidential.

* Indicates a required question

User Agreement

General Research Terms and Conditions^{2*}

- I have read and I accept these Terms and Conditions

Please provide your contact details*:

- First name:
- Email address:

¹ Name hidden for double-blind review purposes. This company is an international IT company specializing in software development.

² Link is removed for double-blind review purpose

Which of the following best describe your job role(s), regardless of your position level? (Select all that apply.)*

- Developer / Programmer / Software Engineer
 - DevOps Engineer / Infrastructure Developer
 - DBA
 - Architect
 - Tester / QA Engineer
 - Technical Writer
 - Technical Support Specialist
 - Data Analyst / Data Engineer / Data Scientist
 - Developer Productivity Engineer / Developer Experience Engineer
 - Team Lead
 - Systems Analyst
 - Business Analyst
 - Product Manager
 - Developer Advocate
 - UX/UI Designer
 - CIO / CEO / CTO
 - Instructor / Teacher / Tutor
 - Other, please specify:
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How many full years of professional software development experience do you have?

- Less than 2 years
- 2–3 years
- 4–6 years
- 7+ years

In which domain or industry do you primarily work?

- Finance / Banking
- Healthcare / Medical
- Automotive / Embedded systems
- Aerospace / Aviation systems
- Defense
- Cybersecurity software
- Enterprise software (non-IT product companies)
- Web / Consumer applications
- IT / Software development industry / Game development industry
- Other, please specify: _____

How often do you use agentic AI tools at work?

- I do not use them at all
- Rarely (less than once a week)
- Occasionally (1–2 times per week)
- Frequently (almost every day)
- Daily

**Which type of AI coding and development assistance do you use at work?
(Select all that apply.)**

- Agents operating on your machine in (plugins for) code editors (*the agent generates and/or edits files*)
- Agents operating on your machine via the CLI or terminal (*the agent generates and/or edits files*)
- Agents operating in cloud environments (e.g. operating on GitHub, GitLab)
- Asking questions or generating code in the AI chat (not in *Agent* mode)
- I don't do AI coding or development

How long have you been using AI tools, including agentic ones?

- Less than 12 months
- 1–2 years
- More than 2 years

Do you use agentic AI tools when reviewing code?

- Yes
- No